

CRITICAL REVIEW ON ARDITA W.S.R TO FACIAL PALSY**¹*Dr. Ratna Gadgil, ²Dr. Vinodini Payghan**¹H.O.D Professor Roga Nidan Vikruti Vijayan Bhausaheb Mulka Ayurved College and Research Centre, Butibori, Nagpur.²Assistant Professor Roga Nidan Vikruti Vijayan Bhausaheb Mulka Ayurved College and Research Centre, Butibori, Nagpur.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Ratna Gadgil**

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INTRODUCTION

Mainly Vata Dosha is the one which acts on nervous system or we can say Vata is nothing but nerve conduction base. Our nervous system controls all motor and sensory system of our body. Vata-which is root of our nervous system and also control the movements of other dosha of human body. Acharya Sushruta explained it in the Vatavyadhi adhyaya of chikitsa sthana. (Ardita is considered as one among the 80 types of Vata Nanatmaja Vyadhi described in our Ayurvedic classics. Ardita with special reference to facial palsy is a disease affecting all ages and more common in the present day scenario which causes distortion of face and associated with the impairment of motor and sensory functions of the affected side of the face, Effective treatment has been highlighted by contemporary science for this crippling disease, by the virtue of targeting the Dosha involved and there by curing the disease through Ayurveda is successful key in the treatment of facial palsy. Various Ayurvedic herbal formulations and Panchakarma procedures have been so far found effective in reversing the condition.

This disease is localized in half of the face with or without the involvement of the body. Arditavata resembles Facial Paralysis or Bell's Phenomenon according to their signs and symptoms, this involves the paralysis of any structures supplied by the facial nerve (7th Cranial nerve). Facial nerve paralysis is characterised by unilateral facial weakness, with other symptoms including (7)-Loss of taste, Decreased salivation, Lacrimation, Mouth deviation etc.

Charak chikitsa sathan

अतिवृद्धः शरीरार्धमेकं वायुः प्रपद्यति । यदा िदोपशोष्यासृग्बाह
ं पादं च जान च ॥३८॥ िस्ममन् सङ्कोचयत्यरे म खं स्रज्हां
करोति च । वक्रिकरोति नासाभूललाटाक्षिह्नूमिथा ॥३९॥ िो
वक्रं व्रजत्यामये भोजनं वक्रनाससकम् । मित्रं नेत्रं कथयिः विथ
श्च तनगृह्णि ॥४०॥ भ ग्रा स्रज्हा सम स्त्िप्ता कला सज्जति चामय
वाक् । दन्िाश्चलस्त्रि बाध्येिे श्रवणौ सभद्यै मवरः ॥४१॥

Vayu affects one half of the face dries up the blood, hand, leg and knee produces contracture in that Half Consequently Nose, Eyebrows, Forehead, Eyes and Jaws get crooked. The Bolus of food goes in mouth in the crooked way, crooked nose, Eyes stiffened and sneezing

is suppressed in spite of impulse. Tongue when raised becomes curved, Voice becomes feeble and impeded, Teeth becomes loose, Hearing is deficient and Voice is hoarse. There is pain in Foot, Hand, Eye, Shank, Thigh, Temple, Ear and cheek. This disease is localised in one-half of the face.

NIDAN (Causative Factor)

Nidana (Causative Factors) Nidana (Causative Factors) according to different Acharyas which one should take care to avoid such diseases because Prevention is better than cure are: Acharya Charaka mentioned suppression of the urge of sneeze, Shiroroga, Carrying heavy loads on head, sudden movement of head and neck, sleeping in an uncomfortable posture, Use of pillows in wrong posture; either too high or too low etc. Acharya Sushruta and Vagbhata said speaking loudly in excess, Churning hard food stuffs, Excessive laughter, yawning and sneezing. Acharya Sushruta added Rakta Kshaya, (depletion of blood) in specific group of patients get afflicted by Arditavata. Pregnant women, recently delivered lady, Children, Old people, Emaciated persons. Acharya Vagbhata explained Arditavata is a disease,

causes due to the vitiation of Pranavata. Yogaratnakara explained Excessive tongue scrapping, Siravyadhana (if done improperly), Injury to the Marmas (Vital points in the head) Excessive rubbing of the eyes, ears and nose, by consuming alcohol and Asavas in excess etc.

▪ **Cervical Branch: Supplies to neck muscles Samprapti (Pathogenesis)**

Purvaroopa (Premonitory Symptoms) and Roopa (Symptoms)

The Poorvarupa and Roopa) of Arditavata described by Acharya Sushruta is as follows: Romaharsha (Horripilation), Vepanam (Tremors), Avila Netrata (Blurred Vision), Toda (Pain), Twachi Swapa (Loss of Sensation of Skin), Vaktrardhavakra (complete or partial loss of voluntary functions of one side of the face), Vaikruta Netradi (Deformities in Eye), Greevachapya (Cervical pain), Vaksanga (Inability to speak), Manya Sthamba (Stiffness Of The Neck), Hanugraha (Stiffness of the Jaw). Sadhyasadyata (Prognosis) If Arditavata is present in patients who are ksheena (debilitated), animesh-aksha (unable to close the eyes), avyakta bhashina (with slurred speech), vepana (tremors), Trivarsha (3years chronicity) or discharge from mouth, eyes and nose is difficult to cure. Spectrum of Vata vyadhis which includes Arditavata can be cured effectively if the patient is Balavana and if the disease is developed recently.

Facial Paralysis

- An inability to move the muscles of the face on one or both sides is known as Facial Paralysis.
- Paralysis of any structures innervated by facial nerve is known as facial paralysis.
- Facial paralysis is due to the lesion of the pyramidal tract between the cortex and the middle of the pons (UMN facial palsy), the nucleus and the 7th cranial nerve (LMN facial palsy)

Facial Nerve

- 7th cranial nerve is mixed nerve (Both sensory & motor functions)
- Its course is divided into two parts:
 1. Intra cranial (Pons to Stylo-mastoid foramen)

2. Extra cranial (After exit from the skull)

Branches of Facial Nerve

- Temporal Nerve: Supplies to frontalis & orbicularis oculi
- Zygomatic Nerve: Supplies to orbicularis oculi
- Buccal Branch: Supplies to upper lip & cheek
- Mandibular Branch: Supplies to lower lip.

Functions of Facial Nerve Each nerve controls

- Eye blinking and closing
- Facial expressions
- Smiling and frowning
- Tear glands
- Salivary glands
- Taste sensations

Symptoms of Facial Palsy

- Unilateral facial weakness
- Loss of taste
- Hyperacusis
- Pain or discomfort in jaw and ear
- Ringing in ears
- Head ache
- Impaired speech
- Difficult eating & drinking
- Excessive tears in one eye

UMN and LMN Facial paralysis can be manifested by two kinds of lesions

1. Supra nuclear lesion (Central / UMN palsy)

Symptoms based on effected lesion

- **Lesion in pons** - Facial sensation loss & drooping may be present hearing.
- **Lesion of chorda tympani** - No salivary secretions
- **Lesion of Stapedius** - Sense of hearing is lost
- **Lesion in corona radiata** - Weakness of face & limbs
- **Lesion in Cerebral cortex** - Weakness of limbs & face, Cognitive dysfunction, Sensory problems, Aphasia Bell's Palsy
- Commonest type of facial palsy
- Major cause of the acute facial nerve paralysis
- It affects totally half side of the face due to the LMN lesion
- Here, the palsy is due to the inflammation of the facial nerve
- The inflammation prevents nerve from sending correct signals to brain & Facial muscles.

Difference between Facial Palsy & Bell's Palsy

Facial Palsy	Bell's Palsy
Causes can be known (Infection, Trauma, Tumor, Infarct)	Idiopathic & may develop suddenly
Permanent (Lasts for years to life)	Temporary (Permanent cure within 3 months in 90% cases)
Need Surgical treatment	Without treatment or surgery regains facial function
Site of affection depends on UMN & LMN lesion	Mainly due to LMN lesions Half side of face is totally affected.

Tests for Facial Palsy

Ask the patient to puff her cheeks

- Ask the patient to show her eyes against resistance
- Ask the patient to lift her eyebrows

Diagnosis

- There are no specific lab tests to confirm the diagnosis.
- ESR for inflammation
- Blood sugar level for diabetes
- Electromyography for nerve damage & determine its severity

Treatment

- **Medical Treatment**

a) Physical therapy

- **MRI & CT scan**

c) Psychotherapy

- **Surgical Treatment**

- a) Nerve decompression
- b) Nerve anastomosis
- c) Nerve grafting

Treatment according to Charak

अर्द्धि नावनं मूस्त्रध िेलं िपधणमेव च ॥९९॥
नाडीमवेदोपनाहाश्चाप्यानूपपसशिर्हीधिः।

In Ardita, Nasya, head oil, Saturation, Tubular Fomentation and Poultices with meat of marshy animals are beneficial.

Treatment principle

- Vata Vriddhi in Kapha Sthanam
- Kapha & Vata Samanam
- Ushna Virya drugs are selected

Treatment**Thalam**

- Rasnadi Choornam with Nimbamrta Eranda Tailam Abhyangam for face
- Karpasastyadi Tailam
- Kshirabaala Tailam

- Dhanwantara Tailam
- Prabanjana Vimardana Tailam

Lepam

Masha / Godhuma is ground in paste and applied over the affected side in the face.

Nadi Swedanam

1. Erandamoola Kashayam / Dasamoola Kashayam / Nirgundi Kashayam

2. **Kshira Dhoomam** with Bala Siddha Kshira Kavalam and Karnapuram Karpasastyadi Tailam Internal medications Kashayam.

- Dhanadanayanadi Kashayam
- Astavarga Kashayam
- Guggulu Tiktaka Kashayam
- Rasonadi Kashayam
- Maharasnadi Kashayam
- Masabalaatmaguptadi Kashayam
- Suntibaladi Kashayam
- Rasnadasamoola kashayam

Siro-Pichu and Siro-Vasti

- Karpasastyadi Tailam
- Dhanwantara Tailam Nasyam
- Karpasastyadi Tailam
- Mahamasha Tailam
- Kshirabala Tailam
- Anu Tailam
- Maharaja Prasarini Tailam Choornam
- Vacha Choorna (2 gms)
- Ashwagandha Choornam - 10 gms HS with milk after food
- Narasimha Choornam - 5 gms hs with milk after food (Cakradatta)
- Svalparasona Pindam - 3 gms with Eranda Kashayam after food

Vati

- Rasonadi Vati (2 bd after food)
- Ekangavira Ras (1 bd after food)
- Brhat Vata Cintamani Ras (125 mg bd after food)
- Vata Gajankusa Ras (125 mg bd after food)
- Samira Pannaga Ras (1 bd after food)
- Vatari Guggulu (1 bd after food)
- Trayodasanga Guggulu (1 bd after food)

Lehyam

- Kalyanaka Avaleham (5 gms bd after food with honey / warm milk)
- Ashwagandha Lehyam (10 gms bd after food)
- Aristam (15 ml bd with water after food)
- Balaristam
- Ashwagandharistam
- Devadarvyaristam
- Saraswatharistam

Single drugs

- Lasuna
- Nirgundi
- Eranda
- Lavanga

- Sarsapa
- Rasna
- Bala
- Ashwagandha
- Vacha
- Guggulu
- Brahmi
- Hingu

Pathya Ahara

- Milk boiled with Dasamoola
- Ghee & butter milk
- Juice of sour fruits
- Navanita with Lasuna
- Mamsa Rasa Vihara
- Residing in places with mild breeze and sunlight
- Chewing bubble gums and blow balloon
- Facial exercises like opening the mouth and eyes as wide as possible & ask them to smile and frown alternatively for 10 -15 mins.

Ideal prescription

- Dhanadanayanadi Kashayam (15 ml with 30 ml water before food bid)
- Ashwagandha Choornam(10 gms HS with milk after food)
- Kalyanaka Avaleham (5 gms bd after food with honey / warm milk)
- Vacha Choornam (locally on tongue)
- Palsinuron cap (1-1-1) after food
- Kshira Bala Tailam for External application

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